

Data Pitch

H2020-ICT-2016-1

Project number: 732506

D6.5 Summary of activities and impact analysis v1

Coordinator: [Ryan Goodman ODI]

**With contributions from: [Helen Desmond & Alex
Vryzakis ODI]**

Quality reviewer: [Stefano SOTON]

Deliverable nature:	Report (R)
Dissemination level: (Confidentiality)	Public (PU)
Nature	Other
Work package	Dissemination and communication (WP6)
Contractual delivery date:	M18
Actual delivery date:	30th June 2018
Version:	V1.0
Keywords:	Dissemination

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1. Executive summary

The dissemination activities of the Data Pitch programme are essential in attaining quality applications in great volume through our open call as well as promoting and supporting the efforts of the accelerated startups and SMEs. This deliverable serves as the summary of activities and impact analysis version 1 report as of June 2018. It gives an overview of dissemination activities that were carried out in the first 18 months of the Data Pitch programme. It focuses on outlining and analysing the impact of the dissemination activities of WP6 and the Data Pitch consortium.

2. Measurable Criteria for Success

2.1. Dissemination & engagement timetable and metrics -

In Deliverable 6.2 “Dissemination, engagement, communication strategy” partners presented the work being led by the Data Pitch communications team, including the efforts and role played by the whole consortium. The previous deliverable focused on the following dissemination, engagement and communication elements:

- Utilising the full reach of the Data Pitch consortium networks
- Community building
- Employing a multi-channel approach
- Strategic media engagement
- Collaboration with other related (EU) projects¹

The following table breaks these elements down into specific activities that have been undertaken by the Data Pitch consortium within the past 18 months. These activities were measured by different consortium members (Data Pitch dissemination team members) on a regular basis, while the results are collected by the dissemination team to analyse the progress and the success, or failure, of the dissemination activities.

These results allow partners to monitor where reworking and/or refining of activities can take place to ensure success in the future. The table is broken down into specific activities associated, their channels and then finally the keys metrics that have been achieved vs those proposed.

Dissemination Activities	Measures	Metrics as of today	Metrics to be achieved by the end of the project
Website	Articles on data economy microsite	>35	70
Social Media	Size of community (Twitter, Facebook followers, mailing list subscribers, Bloggers etc)	> 17.5 (including web users)	10K
	Total Tweets & Blogs	> 950	3K

¹ D6.2 Dissemination, engagement and communication strategy
<https://drive.google.com/drive/search?q=d6.2%20datapitch>

Collaboration and Partnerships	Companies receiving information about the call	>2.5M*	300K
	Competitive call promotion reach	>250M (potential reach identified)*	3M
Training	Peer networking events organised	>10	10
Publications	Press releases	10	10
	Media coverage	80	100

*These reach metrics are estimates based off the number of users and subscribers on partner platforms

3. Overview of activities

3.1. Website

<https://datapitch.eu/>

The project's website was launched in April 2017. It serves as the central access point for anyone seeking to learn about Data Pitch as a project and as an accelerator. It is continuously updated and adapted to reflect current developments within the project, and features information on the consortium partners, startups, deliverables, work packages, and news items. It also contains information on the subject matter of open data and the goals of Data Pitch to foster the European Open Data ecosystem.

Aside from offering comprehensive information on the Data Pitch project and the calls, the website also promotes the other communication and dissemination channels that are in use. On its front page, it links to the Twitter and Facebook accounts (more detail below), and also offers visitors the option to subscribe to the newsletter contact database. Press releases and milestones, as well as materials such as the project's logo and other branded assets, are also communicated through the website.

It documents relevant events and news items regarding the programme. Some resources, such as a privacy toolkit, are available to download.

Statistics for the website:

- 83,284 page views
- 19,158 unique users
- 34,199 sessions
- 2 min 30s average visit duration

As for the numbers that the following part of this report is based on, it is important to note that there are some inherent limitations to the accuracy of the data. Google Analytics is primarily based on cookies and devices. Therefore, one user using several devices (e.g. a laptop and a smartphone) would show up as two users. Similarly, a user that deletes the browser's cookies or uses another browser would also show up as a new user. Furthermore, Google Analytics relies on JavaScript to track users, which is disabled by some, and IF somebody is using an adblock service there would be no data at all. This has an effect on the metrics of total visits and unique indicators. Thus, while the data is the best source of information available, it should not be taken at face value. The data

taken into account here begins in April 2017 in accordance with the website launch.

3.2. Social media

The following social media channels are used:

- Twitter
- Facebook
- Youtube

3.2.1. Twitter

<https://twitter.com/DataPitchEU>

The Twitter account was created at the start of the project in February 2017, in preparation for the launch of the website and to build up community engagement. It allows for direct and instantaneous contact with the various stakeholders in the field of open data, startups and individuals. Whereas the website offers access to in-depth information on all aspects of the project, Twitter is a vehicle for messages and announcements that also functions as a means of keeping track of current developments in the field and direct engagement.

In the last 18 months of the project we gained over 860 followers, posting over 950 tweets in the process. Monthly, we achieve over 20.000 impressions, more than 50 likes and 25 retweets, an average of 15 new followers and 250 profile page views (based on the numbers for the period of January 2018 to May 2018).

For further details see <https://analytics.twitter.com/user/DataPitchEU/home>

In September 2017 we paid for a boosted post campaign. The campaign received 78 link clicks and reached 74,689 people.

We actively monitor Twitter, especially for events and news, as well as harvesting tweets for events and topics to gain further insight.

3.2.2. Facebook Page

<https://www.facebook.com/datapitcheu/>

The Facebook page was created at the beginning of the project. It mirrors the content shared on the website and through Twitter. Its primary purpose is to multiply these messages and increase the reach in order to heighten the penetration of relevant stakeholder groups and having also a presence on this platform. Despite not being a focus in the dissemination strategy, it is regularly updated and contact requests are efficiently replied to in order to ensure that the audiences receive the desired level of attention.

In August-September 2017 we paid for two campaigns which featured the Data Pitch call video. The first campaign was a boosted video post scheduled to be pushed out to all H2020 countries during the period of 15th August - 29th August. It received 25,605 3 second video views and reached 43,753 people. The second campaign was scheduled to once again be pushed out to all H2020 countries during the period of 21st August - 30th September and received 7175 link clicks and reached 105,040 people.

The Facebook page has 138 likes. Analysis has shown that engagement is much lower than on Twitter.

3.2.3. Youtube Channel

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHA-yGRbHgAdB8KqfTs6gyw>

The Data Pitch Youtube channel was established in July 2017. It hosts videos related to the project like explanation of the project, application process and webinars on certain challenges, the promotional video from the Data Pitch Launch event in 2018 and training resources such as workshop recording to enable self study. As a hosting platform, the content can be both implemented in the website and shared across the social media channels. Where relevant, it has been branded with the Data Pitch Logo to align it with the other communication channels.

We have already produced and uploaded more than 10 videos, which together has a combined viewing total of 1,464 views.

3.3. Mailing list

The newsletter is intended to promote important updates and milestones to subscribers. It has been set up to highlight substantial updates on a semi-frequent basis (minimum 12 times per year), therefore complimenting the more continuous flow of information found on the website and the social media channels in a less formal tone than the press releases. Thus far, the newsletter has been promoted on the Twitter page and [the website](#). A sufficient number of subscribers has been collected (currently more than 400) and this channel is serving its purpose as an infrequent announcement tool.

We currently have 3 lists:

- Website sign ups (251)
- Event invitees (96)
- Follow Ups (72)

We have a number of different mailing lists which have different audiences. This enables us to focus on sending through related and relevant content to the applicable audience.

3.4. Events

In order to promote programme activities such as the open call, partners need to ensure dissemination and outreach is maximised. For this to occur, attendance at international conferences is highly recommended. In order to understand what events could be relevant for the programme, partners created a event planner which provides a holistic view of key events Data Pitch should attend.

Other than just promotion, these events provide opportunities for Data Pitch to expand their network creating new ties, the ability to gather input, insights, and new knowledge that is beneficial to the success of such programmes.

During the first 18 months of the programme, Data Pitch members actively participated in a number

of related events. Dissemination activities during those events included distributing general dissemination material such as flyers and stickers, giving presentations, running discussion panels during the events or conducting information sessions during the breaks of these events for the purpose of informing people about the project.

For a list of the events attended see Appendix 5.1 for Past events attended and 5.2 for upcoming events.

3.5. Collaboration and partnerships

To promote Data Pitch and strengthen the emphasis on corporates sharing data, partnerships and and collaborations were sought with similar initiatives or relevant organisations within the ecosystem, these include:

- Open Data Incubator for Europe (ODINE) Cross-promotional efforts as well as presentations and events
- European Data Science Academy (EDSA) Cross-promotional efforts as well as Data Science related training for startups
- European Data Incubator (EDI) - Cross-promotional efforts as well as presentations and events
- EIT Digital - Cross-promotional efforts as well as presentations and events
- BDVE - Cross-promotional efforts and working with members from the Public Private Partnership (PPP) monitoring group
- Deutsche Bahn - Data and challenge provider for the first open call, cross promotion of events (Berlin hackathon)
- Sonae - Data and challenge provider for the first open call
- IMIN - Data and challenge provider for the first open call
- Spazio-dati - Data and challenge provider for the first open call
- Uniserv - Data and challenge provider for the first open call

3.6. Training

The following training is offered by the Data Pitch consortium;

- Data Innovation Academy, training on topics such as;
 - Data science and skills
 - Open data
 - Digital business skills
 - Business innovation
 - Legal and privacy matters pertaining to data sharing and use

Additionally, there are several webinars and online resources that are provided to startups. These can be accessed at any time, and enable startups to learn at a self guided pace. These webinars include; B2B Sales, How to get word of mouth for your startup and understanding GDPR.

For more training details, see Deliverable D6.4 Training curriculum, learning materials and webinar in details.

3.7. Deliverables

Below is a full list of the completed deliverables so far in the programme:

- D1.1 Project fact sheet & internal communication tools
- D1.2 Data management plan
- D2.1 DaaS platform
- D2.2 EaaS facilities and support
- D2.3 Updated DaaS platform
- D3.1 Legal and privacy toolkit v1
- D3.2 Data catalogue and documentation v1
- D3.3 Data legality report v1
- D3.4 First Data Pitch consultations
- D3.5 Legal and privacy toolkit v2
- D3.6 Data catalogue and documentation v2
- D3.8 Second Data Pitch consultations
- D4.1 Call definition
- D4.2 Summary of round 1
- D5.1 Incubation services
- D5.2 Experiments oversight tools
- D5.3 Round 1: final review
- D6.1 Online presence and marketing tools
- D6.2 Dissemination, engagement, communication strategy
- D6.3 Advisory board
- D6.4 Training curriculum, learning materials, and webinars
- D6.5 Summary of activities and impact analysis v1
- D7.1 Exploitation strategy
- D7.2 Impact assessment framework
- D7.3 Sustainability strategy and implementation roadmap
- D8.1 POPD - Requirement No.2
- D8.2 POPD - Requirement No.4

3.8. Publications

We are reaching out to targeted business, technology and sector specific media publications with compelling stories about startups, data providers and the data ecosystem. We are also placing byline articles which show thought leadership on the data European data ecosystem space in leading titles.

3.9. Findings and improvements for the 2nd period

In the first period of the programme, we have focused on establishing Data Pitch as a strong and recognised brand. The intention now is to focus on share our experience and learnings about the

innovation model. By establishing relationships with the different stakeholders from the European data economy community, we will be able to share the stories of success in the help drive change within the community, for organisations to become more open to sharing data.

In order to drive this change, we must focus on supporting the startups via the accelerator by helping them grow and succeed. By improving the growth of the Data Pitch startups, we will have more concrete evidence and validation that innovation can be directly benefit the organisations who share the data.

To maximise the impact on the data community and the startups within our programme, the consortium partners will need to seek and fund more startups to prove this concept. To ensure maximum reach and an increase in the uptake of applications, we will focus on using F6S to scout relevant and suitable startups for the second call.

4. Summary

This report has documented the dissemination activities and materials in the first 18 month period of the Data Pitch programme. The dissemination and communication of the programme and its (future) results took off with the first announcement of the programme back in February 2016.

Following the initial announcement, the communication channels follow an upward trend in terms of the users and level of outreach generated. The communication strategy set out that Data Pitch should produce a constant communication stream on social media, and blogs on its website.

The results from this report show that in terms of the streaming, Twitter is the most efficient social media dissemination tool for generating outreach for the success of the participant organisations. As our twitter audience mainly consists of stakeholder in the European Startup landscape.

This report also highlights the importance of seeking newsworthy and publishable content to target policy makers and to drive the mentality of public sector organisations and corporates to becoming more open to sharing data for the benefit of innovation.

Furthermore, the website has performed reasonably well and is a centralised location for content, contacts and online resources. The Facebook and LinkedIn accounts are set up, but are now mostly used to bring the existing content to a different user group. The efforts for both LinkedIn and Facebook will be further increased. The Youtube channel is successful and will get further content in the future via the webinars.

The consortium has participated in several high-profile conferences, workshops and events in addition to the organized events such as the Kick off event and Demonstration Day in 2018. The success shows in the number of stakeholder attendees.

5. Appendix

5.1. Past events attended

The following events were attended by the Data Pitch consortium partners to promote the programme.

Pixel Camp	Lisbon	September 2017
Bitz & Pretzels	Munich	September 2017
Stockholm Tech Fest	Stockholm	September 2017
Tech BBQ	Copenhagen	September 2017
Pirate Summit	Cologne	September 2017
Web Summit	Lisbon	November 2017
EBDVF	Paris	December 2017
Slush	Helsinki	December 2017
Oascities	Brussels	January 2018
Agoria. Smartcities	Brussels	March 2018
Antimicrobial resistance workshop	London	March 2018
EU Startup Summit	Barcelona	April 2018
InfoShare	Gdansk	May 2018
The Next Web (TNW)	Amsterdam	May 2018
Lisbon Investment Summit	Lisbon	June 2018

5.2. Upcoming events

Following events we have identified and look to have a representation at for the near future:

Pirate Summit	Cologne	July 2018
Unbound	London	July 2018
DLD Digital	Tel Aviv	September 2018
StartupFest Europe	Amsterdam	September 2018
Sthlm Tech Fest 2018	Stockholm	September 2018
Next Conference	Reeperbahn	September 2018
ODI Summit	London	November 2018
Web Summit	Lisbon	November 2018
EDF	Vienna	November 2018
How to web	Bucharest	November 2018
ICT 2018	Vienna	December 2018

A full list of targeted events can be found in the [Data Pitch events](#) list.